

Quantum Free Particle Wavepacket, Classical Probability and Information

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 3, 2024

In (1), it is suggested that one may create a quantum free particle wavepacket with a $t=0$ value of:

$$W(x,0) = C \exp(im_0 vx) \exp(-(x-x_0)^2/C^2)$$

which leads to $W^*(x,t)W(x,t) = 1/\sqrt{(3.14)(C^2+C^2t^2)} \exp\{-(x-v_0t)^2/(C^2+C^2t^2)\}$.

The authors of (1) note that one may establish a strictly classical probability using a Gaussian for $P(x_{\text{initial}})$ and a Gaussian for $P(v_{\text{initial}})$. Then using $x_f = x_i + vt$, one may write:

$$P_{\text{final}}(x, t) = \int P_{\text{initial}}(x-vt) P_{\text{initial}}(v) dv = 1/\sqrt{(3.14)(C^2+C^2t^2)} \exp\{-(x-v_0t)^2/(C^2+C^2t^2)\},$$

This result matches the quantum mechanics free wavepacket one.

We argue that even though classical and quantum interpretations and x, t are different, one may obtain the same results in the case of averages. For example, for a bound state at any energy level, $KE_{\text{classical}}(x) = -1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W$.

In the case considered in (1), the classical view is that one may follow any particle with an x_{initial} and constant v_{initial} , through $x_{\text{final}} = x_{\text{initial}} + v_{\text{initial}} t$. If, however, one removes information about initial and v_{initial} by using Gaussians, i.e. by using a distribution which removes bias, then all of the deterministic information is removed from the classical scenario. One no longer really has $x_f = x_i + vt$. Unlike the quantum case, however, one has no notion of wavelength and frequency.

In the quantum scenario, a particle with momentum p , may be represented by $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$. We argue that t and x are decoupled and that the particle may be at any t and x with the same modulus probability. \hbar/E yields t resolution and \hbar/p , x resolution. One does not obtain v using $d(-Et+px)=0$. Thus, the quantum scenario does not follow the particle in time and space, but is concerned with a physical wavelength \hbar/p (and \hbar/E) which is not found in the classical scenario. Thus, quantum mechanics, even for a given E, p , treats any x and t as having the same modulus probability, but there is still the wavelength-frequency information. If one removes this information by creating a linear summation which is a Gaussian, as in (1), then $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ yields spatial and time probability with no classical $x = x_i + vt$ information and no particular \hbar/p , \hbar/E information.

We argue that if one takes the classical picture, $x_f = x_i + vt$, and removes the classical features of following the particle in time, through the use of x_i and v following Gaussian distributions and there is no wavelength-frequency information to begin with, and if one takes a quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which already decouples x, t and does not use $x_f = x_i + vt$, and removes \hbar/E and \hbar/p information through Gaussians, then in both cases one is left with the same amount of information and so has the same result for $P(x_f, t)$ or $W^*(x, t)W(x, t)$ as pointed out in (1).

As an added note, $\exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L}\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$, a quantum result already matches the classical $P(x)dx=dx/L$ result. Thus, the fact that the quantum wavepacket (W^*W) matches a classical result is anticipated in a certain sense.

Classical Mechanics Versus Quantum Mechanics

Classical mechanics follows a particle in space and time and uses:

$$X_{\text{final}} = x_{\text{initial}} + vt \quad ((1))$$

If, however, one does not know x_{initial} and v constant, one has essentially removed the determinism of classical mechanics. In particular, x_{initial} may be picked using a Gaussian distribution and v as well. This is no longer a classical deterministic scenario, but rather a classical statistical one.

We note that there is another classical statistical scenario:

$$P(x)dx = dx/L \quad ((2))$$

This simply states that a particle may be at any x point in L with the same probability.

In previous notes, we have introduced the quantum free particle (constant p) probability $\exp(ipx)$ as one which ensures conservation of momentum by introducing a second variable x and using orthogonality in space. We note that $\exp(ipx)$ is already linked to the classical ((2)) through:

$$\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L} \exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L} \quad ((3))$$

One may generalize $\exp(ipx)$ to $\exp(ipx)\exp(-iEt)$ ((4)). The point we wish to make is that x and t are decoupled in ((3)). One does not have $x/t=v$ and each t and x has the same modulus probability. The key feature, which goes beyond classical mechanics is that there is a specific wavelength and frequency:

$$\hbar/p \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \hbar/E \quad ((5b))$$

Even though x and t appear in ((4)), the interpretation differs from the classical one. It is, however, linked to the classical ((2)) in which one does not know where the particle is, or even its p as ((3))=((2)) for all p . The issue, as we noted, is that the quantum $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ contains ((5a)) and ((5b)) information not present in the classical picture. If one could remove this information, and at the same time remove x_{initial} and v information from the classical picture, the two pictures would represent the same amount of information, it seems. (The results of (1) bear this out.)

Approach of (1)

One treats the classical scenario in the following manner. ((1)) is the starting point, but it is assumed that x_{initial} and v follow Gaussian distributions which have the least bias, i.e.

$$P(x_{\text{initial}}) = C \exp(- (x_{\text{initial}} - x_0)^2 / C2) \quad ((6a)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$P(v) = C3 \exp(- (v-v_0)^2 / C4) \quad ((6b))$$

The overall probability for $P(x_{\text{final}})$ is:

$$P(x_{\text{final}})(x,t) = \int P(x_{\text{initial}}(x-vt)) P(v) dv \quad \text{where } x_{\text{initial}} = x_{\text{final}} - vt = x - vt \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{This yields: } P(x,t)_{\text{final}} = 1/\sqrt{(3.14)(C3+C4t)} \exp\{- (x-vt)^2 / (C3+C4t)\}, \quad ((8))$$

Basically, one has removed all determinism from the classical picture and this same picture has no notion of $\hbar/p = \text{wavelength}$ or $\hbar/E = \text{frequency}$ to begin with. Thus, ((8)) is a statistical result with determinism removed and no quantum features.

The question is then: What information does a quantum mechanical approach contain?

We argue that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ does not consider $x = x_{\text{initial}} + vt$ because one does not follow a particle in x,t . Rather x and t are decoupled and there exists equal modulus probability for any t and x . In addition, there are the nonclassical results ((5a)) and ((5b)), which make quantum mechanics more general than classical mechanics.

In terms of information, it seems that the loss of information linked to $x_{\text{final}} = x_i + vt$ is already gone from quantum mechanics, but there is the extra \hbar/p , \hbar/E information, needed to ensure momentum and energy conservation. We note that conservation of energy and momentum already appear in classical mechanics and so $\exp(ipx)$ actually follows from a classical idea.

We argue that if one removes \hbar/p , \hbar/E information, then the classical $x_f = x_i + vt$ information removal of the classical scenario performed in (1) should match the quantum result W^*W , with \hbar/p , \hbar/E information removed. Again, one uses the idea of Gaussians.

In (1), it is assumed that at $t=0$, the quantum wavefunction for noninteracting free particles (i.e. a wavepacket) is:

$$W(x,t=0) = C \exp(im_0 vx) \exp(-(x-x_0)^2 / C2) \quad ((9))$$

According to (1) and other calculations of free particle wavepackets,

$$W(x,t) = \sqrt{m / (2 \cdot 3.14 \hbar i t)} \int W(y,0) \exp(im (x-y)(x-y) / (2\hbar t)) dy \quad ((10))$$

((10)) yields:

$$W^*(x,t)W(x,t) = 1/\sqrt{(3.14)(C3+C4t)} \exp\{- (x-vt)^2 / (C3+C4t)\} \quad ((11))$$

((11)), however, is the exact result ((8)) because both contain the same information, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have argued that one may obtain the quantum mechanical free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ from the classical notion of conservation of momentum. In order to impose this condition, one is required to introduce a second variable x to create an orthogonality condition. This leads to the idea of a wavelength \hbar/p from $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, $\exp(ipx)$ follows from the classical notion of conservation of momentum and is a kind of probability with certain features, but is more general than classical mechanics.. In particular, one may extend it to $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$. In such a case, x and t are decoupled and yield the same modulus weight for each t,x as well as the information: \hbar/E , \hbar/p . Given the probabilistic nature of this approach, one does not follow a particle in time through $xf = xi + vt$.

Newtonian mechanics, however, does follow a particle thorough $xf=xi+vt$. If one tries to lose this deterministic information, as done in (1), by treating xi and v as following Gaussian distributions, then one no longer has classical determinism, but one also has no notion of \hbar/p and \hbar/E .

If one takes $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and creates weights in keeping with a Gaussian distribution at $t=0$, and lets this evolve in time (see (1)), one begins with x and t decoupled and no $xf=xi+vt$ and also removes \hbar/p and \hbar/E in the least biased way. In such a case, we argue that the remaining information should be equivalent to the information in $P(xf,t)$ by treating xi and v as Gaussian variables. In other words, statistical approaches are linked to information and we have argued that the quantum mechanical $\exp(ipx)$ is created to ensure classical conservation of momentum. In addition, is already associated with $P(x)dx=dx/L$, $L=length$, a classical result, because $\exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L}\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}=1/L$. In this form, however, p seems to disappear, but is really still present as seen from 2-slit interference. Thus, one needs to create a wavepacket in order to really remove the information of \hbar/p , \hbar/E as done in (1).

References

1. Aldo Arroyo E. Exploring the Transition between Classical and Quantum Mechanics (May 30, 2024)
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/reader/977175fdd5c319a483612050bd2b28b83251918f>